

Initial Validation of the TRIGA Real-Time Digital Twin at the University of Texas at Austin

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20804160

ABSTRACT

A reduced-order model (ROM) for real-time neutron flux prediction in the University of Texas TRIGA reactor has been developed and validated against experimental measurements at two distinct core locations. The ROM is constructed using Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD) applied to high-fidelity MPACT neutronics simulations, producing a computationally efficient representation suitable for digital twin applications. Validation efforts focused on two complementary measurement locations that test different aspects of the ROM's predictive capability. First, the ROM was validated against neutron monitor (NM) measurements, which respond primarily to thermal flux and provide the calibrated signal used for reactor power monitoring. Close agreement between ROM predictions and NM readings throughout power transients demonstrates that the ROM accurately captures local thermal flux dynamics at instrumented locations. Second, the ROM was validated against neutron activation measurements in the Fast 3-Element (F3EL) experimental facility, which features a hardened neutron spectrum enriched in fast neutrons relative to typical TRIGA core locations. Accurate reproduction of the full flux spectrum confirms that the ROM correctly predicts both the magnitude and energy distribution of the neutron flux. Together, these validations spanning thermal-dominated and fast-spectrum environments demonstrate the ROM's fidelity for digital twin applications including real-time monitoring, virtual sensing, and experiment planning.

Keywords: Digital Twin, Reduced Order Model, TRIGA

1. INTRODUCTION

A digital twin (DT) is a dynamic, data-driven computational representation of a physical asset with bidirectional flow of information between digital and physical components. The digital twin concept has matured from industrial and aerospace origins into a powerful framework for nuclear reactor state estimation, control, and predictive modeling. By coupling high-fidelity multiphysics simulation with real-time sensor data, digital twins bridge the gap between computational modeling and plant operation, allowing reactor systems to be characterized, predicted, and optimized at faster-than-real-time timescales [1].

Recent advances in high-performance computing (HPC), reduced-order modeling (ROM), and machine learning (ML) have lowered computational barriers for digital twin development and deployment. The University of Texas (UT) at Austin's *Digital Molten Salt Reactor Initiative (DMSRI)* is leveraging these advances to develop DT and digital-shadow architectures for molten-salt and nuclear systems, using the TRIGA Mark II at the Nuclear Engineering Teaching Laboratory (NETL) as a testbed. The UT TRIGA research reactor provides a controlled environment in which models, data pipelines, and control logic can be tested and validated before their possible extension to molten salt reactor (MSR) systems.

Recent efforts have demonstrated integration of raw console data ingestion to produce high-fidelity simulations using MPACT [2], which in turn is used to produce ROMs that can make faster-than-real-time predictions [3].

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1.1. The NETL TRIGA Reactor

The UT Austin TRIGA Mark II is a pool-type research reactor located at NETL, approximately ten miles north of UT's main campus. Fueled with 8.5 wt% U–ZrH alloy (19.7 wt% U-235 enrichment), it employs natural convection cooling and five experimental beam ports penetrating the graphite reflector for neutron-beam and gamma-irradiation experiments. It has four control rods — three of which are fuel-followed and one that air followed. One of the fuel-followed rods is called the regulating rod (RR), and serves as the regulating rod and can be operated in a proportional-integral-differential (PID) feedback loop to maintain a desired power level. The other two fuel-followed rods are shim rod 1 (S1) and shim rod 2 (S2), and are typically parked during steady power operations, and inserted or withdrawn for power maneuvers. The air-followed rod is the transient rod (TR) and can be used to rapidly pulse the reactor, but is also often moved manually for making smaller adjustments to reactivity.

Unlike commercial reactors, the UT TRIGA operates intermittently, generally 8 hours per day, with power levels adjusted based on the needs of daily experiments. Because of this operating pattern, ^{135}Xe concentrations never reach equilibrium, and only approach zero after a multi-day shutdown. The daily startup and frequent power maneuvers along with the reactor's inherent safety features make it an ideal environment for exploring digital twin concepts.

The reactor operates at a nominal power of 1.1 MW, though it typically runs closer to 900 kW. Recent studies revealed power-signal fluctuations of up to $\pm 15\%$ during steady-state operation [4]. Fourier analysis attributed the dominant frequencies to detector-electronic noise and electromagnetic interference from regulating-rod control magnets. Recalibration reduced fluctuations to $\pm 6\%$, improving data quality for DT validation.

Instrumentation includes an ex-core fission chamber neutron monitor (NM), and two ex-core ion chambers. The NM is used for measuring reactor power and is calibrated using pool calorimetry. The console data also includes fuel temperature measurements from a two instrumented fuel elements (IFE), a pool-temperature thermocouple, and control-rod position indicators for the four control rods.

1.2. The Reduced-Order Model Digital Twin

The DT framework uses the deterministic transport code MPACT for high-fidelity calculations and a reduced-order model capable of faster-than-real-time execution. Although MPACT is a high-fidelity full multiphysics reactor simulator, its execution time is not fast enough to be used for real-time applications. MPACT serves as the generator of training data for the ROM. The ROM, in turn, approximates those dynamics within a low-dimensional subspace, allowing rapid prediction, state reconstruction, and control. In this framework, deterministic physics codes supply detailed snapshots of system evolution and data-driven surrogates (ROMs, ML networks) supply speed and adaptability [5, 6].

Early ROM efforts used proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) and long short-term memory (LSTM) neural networks to reconstruct time-dependent flux distributions from limited sensor data [3]. Subsequent studies extended this approach through dynamic mode decomposition (DMD), yielding a multiphysics ROM that simultaneously tracks multigroup flux, pin power, and fuel temperature with flux errors below 1.3% [7]. These reduced-order frameworks advance the reactor state using explicit linear operators informed by control-rod motion and power feedback, enabling faster-than-real-time evaluation on modest hardware. In addition, the ROMs can be embedded within model predictive control (MPC) loops for automated rod-motion optimization. Together, these ROM-based methods transform the TRIGA DT from a static emulator into an active predictive engine capable of forecasting reactor behavior and suggesting optimal control actions.

Figure 1. Diagram illustrating the cycle of digital twin development and deployment.

1.3. Digital Shadow and Digital Twin Deployment

A digital twin is a digital representation of a physical object where data flow bidirectionally between the two objects, and each object fully integrates the available data. A digital shadow is a digital representation of a physical object in which data flow only from the physical to the digital object [8]. Creating a digital shadow can be a useful step in developing and deploying digital twins. An automation code called *Shadowcaster* was developed for the UT TRIGA digital shadow. Shadowcaster performs many tasks to coordinate the digital shadow execution including: nightly data transfers from the locally hosted data acquisition computer to the Lonestar-6 supercomputer at the Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC), performing off-line change-point detection of the reactor power and control rod signals, automatically constructing new MPACT input files based on daily operational conditions, submitting computing jobs to Lonestar-6 the Slurm queuing system, and reporting key outputs from the executed jobs. [9]. When fully developed, the digital shadow will automatically produce newly trained ROMs for testing and operational deployment.

Figure 1 illustrates how the UT TRIGA reactor, the high-fidelity digital shadow, and the reduced order model real time digital twin are cyclically developed and deployed. The foundation of the diagram is the physical twin which provides operational data. These data are combined with expert knowledge, including historical records, material compositions, and core geometry, to construct high-fidelity models used by the physics-driven digital shadows of the reactor. After the high-fidelity models are validated against the operational data to ensure the models accurately represent the physical system, these models can be used to train reduced-order models (ROMs) or data-driven models. High-fidelity models not only regularly generate training data, but they also allow synthetic data to be generated for off-normal or rarely observed reactor states, which can ensure the training data for the reduced-order models is robust. Finally, the real-time digital twins created from this process are used to support reactor operations a decision-support tool helping plan optimal control rod movements and for predicting local neutron spectra at beamlines and experiment irradiation locations.

2. COMPARISON OF DIGITAL TWIN PREDICTIONS TO MEASUREMENTS

2.1. Neutron Flux at Locations

2.1.1. Thermal Flux at NM Detector

Figure 2 demonstrates that the ROM accurately reproduces the neutron flux at the neutron monitor (NM) location during an ascent to full power maneuver. The NM is a standard fission chamber that reads thermal flux, which it converts to a total power estimate through calibrated scaling based on the approximately constant ratio between thermal flux at the detector location and total core power. The close ROM-NM agreement validates that the ROM correctly captures the local flux behavior governing the instrument response used for reactor power monitoring. This validation is particularly significant because the NM location represents a challenging test case for the ROM, requiring accurate prediction of not only the total fission rate, but also the spatial flux distribution and energy spectrum at a specific point in the reactor. The thermal flux at the detector location is sensitive to local moderator conditions, control rod positions, and neutron thermalization. The ROM's ability to reproduce these measurements demonstrates that the spatial modes and temporal dynamics extracted from the training data successfully encode the physics governing flux redistribution during transients. Furthermore, accurate reproduction of NM readings is essential for real-time digital twin applications, where the ROM must predict the same quantities measured by physical instrumentation to enable meaningful comparison and state estimation. The agreement shown in Figure 2 confirms that the ROM can serve as a reliable virtual sensor, predicting instrument responses with sufficient fidelity to support model-based monitoring and control strategies.

Figure 2. Thermal Flux at NM During Approach to Power

2.2. Neutron Spectra at 3-EL In-Core Irradiation Facility

2.2.1. Experimental Apparatus and Method

The Fast 3-Element (F3EL) facility is a removable irradiation filter designed to approximate a Watt fission neutron energy spectrum for use in the 3-element position in the University of Texas TRIGA reactor core. The F3EL contains two cylindrical aluminum annuli packed with boron powder to absorb thermal neutrons. The lower annulus, which sits between the core grid plates when the facility is installed, is packed with enriched ^{10}B powder and wrapped with a cadmium sleeve to minimize thermal neutron incursion to the sample irradiation location. The upper annulus, which sits just above the upper core grid plate, is packed with natural B_4C to shield samples from thermal neutrons as they make their rapid exit from the irradiation location via the attached pneumatic system.

Two pneumatic rabbit materials are available for sample irradiation in this facility. Polyether ether ketone (PEEK) contains manufacturing impurities that experience significant activation but can be used at all available reactor power levels due to its high continuous use temperature. Low-density polyethylene (LDPE) activates minimally and is better suited to immediate in-situ sample measurement but is limited to a maximum of 250 kW reactor power due to facility heating. Flux monitors consisting of a variety of well-characterized, high purity metals and alloys were irradiated in each type of rabbit and counted on a shielded HPGe detector to measure neutron activation for both broad spectrum and threshold reactions. Experimental results were fitted to an MCNP6 model of the facility flux with STAYSL PNNL. STAYSL PNNL is a neutron dosimetry and spectral unfolding software suite distributed by Pacific Northwest National lab that uses a least squares fit to produce a recommended neutron flux spectrum for use in future experiment calculations.

Accurate reproduction of the neutron energy spectrum at the F3EL location is critical for ROM validation because reaction rates are determined by the convolution of energy-dependent cross-sections with the local flux spectrum. The ROM's ability to predict the correct reaction rates across a wide range of energies demonstrates that it captures the energy distribution in addition to the spatial distribution. This spectral accuracy is essential for digital twin applications involving material dosimetry, transmutation calculations, and experimental planning. The F3EL facility provides a particularly stringent test of the ROM's spectral fidelity because its hardened spectrum differs significantly from the thermal-dominated spectrum at the NM location, requiring the ROM to correctly predict spatial variations in neutron thermalization throughout the core.

3. DIGITAL TWIN PREDICTIVE CAPABILITIES

Integration of faster-than-real-time predictive models for full-core flux distribution represents a potentially significant advancement in NETL TRIGA reactor operations. This capability enables proactive evaluation of reactor behavior under various control strategies and improve overall operational planning.

The most fundamental application of this predictive capability is in conducting operational scoping studies. Using the current ROM, operators may simulate a planned sequence of control actions and observe the corresponding reactor response prior to execution. While predicting global power behavior is the most basic outcome, the ROM also provides detailed flux distributions throughout the core, allowing targeted queries at specific locations. This functionality supports flux tuning for irradiation experiments by enabling evaluation of spectral changes before and after a maneuver, a capability that was not previously available at NETL. An example of this process is shown in Figure 4, where the ROM can display the multigroup flux at both instrumentation and experimental locations. Furthermore, as maneuvers are executed, predictions can be made in real-time, allowing operators to make course corrections or rerun simulations if conditions suddenly change or deviations are detected.

More advanced applications arise when the ROM is coupled with control schemes such as a Model Pre-

Figure 3. Flux spectrum comparison at 100kW between 100-group STAYSL and 51-group MPACT/ROM.

Figure 4. ROM Predicted 3-Group Flux Collapsed from Full 51-Group Solution

dictive Control (MPC) framework [10]. In this configuration, the controller uses ROM-based forecasts to optimize control actions against a defined cost function over a finite prediction horizon, subject to operational constraints such as rod movement limits, ramp rates, and safety margins. This approach enables automatic generation of control plans for achieving specific reactor objectives, such as improved power ascension profiles or targeted flux shaping at experimental locations. Digitally enhanced experiment planning may also enable profiles that would be difficult to execute manually, such as the double square wave shown in Figure 5a. While the NETL TRIGA is not currently licensed for full automation of safety-related systems, limited automated control can be implemented using non-safety-related components. For example, NETL plans to install a low-worth aluminum power-smoothing rod to mitigate the aforementioned power fluctuations that currently constrain maximum operating power. In this

configuration, operators would specify a target power level, and the controller would automatically adjust the smoothing rod to minimize fluctuations, allowing operation closer to the licensed power limit. An example of this implementation is illustrated in Figure 5b. These examples represent only a subset of the operational enhancements enabled by this faster-than-real-time predictive modeling, with additional capabilities anticipated as the framework matures.

Figure 5. MPC Performance for Digital Twin Control

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents an initial assessment of the NETL TRIGA digital twinning pipeline by evaluating ROM predictions against measured reactor responses. In addition to this validation, several near-term operational capabilities enabled by the ROM were simulated, including forward planning, automated control plan generation, and partially automated control. Once fully deployed, these capabilities are expected to support more efficient operational planning, reduce the currently applied full-power buffer margin, and enable real-time flux tuning to support experimental objectives. The next step in this effort is the full integration of these features into routine operations.

Further development of the framework is expected to enable additional functionality. One concept under consideration is an operator-assist capability analogous to driver-assist systems. In this approach, the ROM-MPC framework would be provided a planned maneuver and then would monitor real-time control actions and project reactor responses on-the-fly. If predicted behavior diverges from a predefined tolerance band, the system could notify operators and recommend corrective actions to maintain alignment with the intended trajectory.

Although this study focuses on the NETL TRIGA reactor, the digital twinning pipeline is designed for adaptability to other research reactors and, potentially, commercial power reactors. While the pipeline is not intended for licensing or direct safety-related control, the ROMs produced can serve as valuable

guidance and planning tools. For research reactors, online flux tuning can enhance irradiation outcomes and improve experiment design. In commercial applications, high-resolution flux predictions could support strategies to minimize localized fuel stress and provide more accurate post-irradiation isotopic estimates for improving fuel cycle planning and utilization. Additionally, retrospective analysis of detailed flux distributions could accelerate identification of failed fuel rods by locating instances of localized flux peaking in historical operational data.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is funded by the University of Texas Digital Molten Salt Reactor Initiative supported by the State of Texas. <http://nucleartwins.tacc.utexas.edu>

The authors acknowledge the Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC) at The University of Texas at Austin for providing computational resources that have contributed to the research results reported within this paper. <http://www.tacc.utexas.edu>

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